

→ MESS0018: GEO 2.2 - Magnetic Anomalies in VA and KY ¹

Complete Bouguer Gravity Anomaly Map of Virginia

by Stephen L. Snyder

- Industrial Minerals (Feldspar, Mica, Kyanite, Vermiculite, Barite)
- Metals (Iron, Manganese, Copper, Gold, Pyrite, Tungsten)
- Building Stone (Granite, Slate, Marble)
- Aggregate

MESS 0029

GEO 2.25: Hyperfocus on the Blue Ridge Mountains Anomaly; magnetic, gravitic, magma, mineral, and water studies within the flux and Virginia Piedmont

Sf. R. Careaga, BSEE, MSTOM

November 2022

ABSTRACT

Previous MESSy electrogeology papers focused on wider observations; while there are moments of strong focus, they remain somewhat topical. This paper utilizes overlays to demonstrate the improbability and even impossibility of standard model geology in explaining the anomalies present. This opens the wide opportunity for EGM to explain what we observe at Shenandoah National Park.

Keywords: Bouguer - Gravity - Anomaly - Magnetic - Mineralogy - Piedmont - Mesozoic - Blue Ridge chain

¹ Figure 1 - Super Overlay from Figures 7-9 of MESSy #18; gravity over magnetic over mineral with a red annulus of focus; credit: author/Snyder/Nature/USGS

Recollection

If the reader will recall, in MESSy #18, there was a topological, macroscopic and ultimately macrolytic examination of the magnetic and gravity anomalies associated with the Blue Ridge Mountains. The MESSies to follow were then systematically examining EGM hypotheses, and assertions, while recording findings that were over a year old; the most important and solid being the Hall-Yelverton Crooked Smile Keystone found at the Pine Mountain Flux, and the solid EGM electroneogenesis of the long track tornado of Dec.10, 2021 that devastated Mayfield, KY. However, although the author’s work centers on Kentucky, there was something unique about the circled area in Figure 1 (cover page), which warranted deeper speculation and attention. It was epitomized in this way: gravity and magnetic anomalies did not appear to obey external geometric, geological formation, nor mineral morphology, per se. And although there is some mineralogical cause of magnetic escarpments and concentrations, the research into the Arkansas/New Madrid Seismic Zone area left us with even more questions than answers.

One thing that is seriously clear is that standard geology has no accounting for any of this because it is way outside of their norms of understanding; outside of “within normal limits.” In that way, this region might be considered a geological OOPart. At any rate, the author intends to dive in with as much detail as possible at this stage of publicly available technology, and try to make sense of this. It might very well be that we are looking at some form of wye circuit presentation, literally and figuratively.

Figure 2 - Virginia topological; credit: google (click image to expand)

Below, next 2 pages:

- ❖ Figure 3 - “Complete Bouguer Gravity Anomaly Map of Virginia”; credit: S. Snyder
 - ❖ Figure 4 - Magnetic Anomaly Map of Virginia; credit: Nature Reviews
 - ❖ Figure 5 - Hyper focus on Annulus for mineralogy; credit: USGS/Stose & Ljungstedt²
 - ❖ Figure 6 - Mineral materium map for Virginia; credit: energy.virginia.gov³
- (click image to open interactive map)

² <https://i.redd.it/89g6rx8939t51.jpg> (6000px HD; click link or image to enlarge)

³ <https://www.energy.virginia.gov/geology/geologymineralresources.shtml>

MIMS 2.10.13⁴ *applied...* hyper investigation into the Blue Ridge-Piedmont Anomalies.

Complete Bouguer Gravity Anomaly Map of Virginia
by Stephen L. Snyder

Copyright © 2005 Nature Publishing Group
Nature Reviews | Neuroscience

⁴ MIMS 2.10.1-.3 - MESS0025: Investigation - Sir Arthur's Gift

New Overlays & Brief Analysis

Figure 7 - The Bouguer Anomaly cuts across the Blue Ridge Flow, and although there are densities of gravity within the Mesozoic Basins, the anomalies appear to have little bearing directly to do with differentiation of the Piedmont and coastal plains. The BA escarpment is centered (as an arc) right at the Shenandoah, where “volcanic” minerals are found. That is to say, the author theorizes that electric transmutations occurred at specific strike points. Note that the Buzzard rock and ridges near the Seven Bends State Park have no bearing on the BA. Credit: author et al.

Figure 8 - Similar overlay, but mineralogical with zoom in on figure 6; From top arrow to bottom: bifurcation, Shenandoah “volcanism”, BA crosses from Piedmont to Coastal Plain; credit: author, et al.

We can see the aforementioned (#18) gravitic bifurcation in the Mesozoic layer, which as it is at a completely different vector from the BRM chain. Certainly it is interesting. From an electrogravitic theory presentation, the author must hypothesize that we are seeing *remnant* concentrations and escarpments that are divided across the previously existing layer (stratigro-chemico-geological morphology) which was involved in the uplift of the BRM chain, and the *apparent* appearance of ancient volcanism. But in fact, the arc-EDM of the chain was peaking at the Shenandoah, as a moving anode, leaving these anomalies in the layers as its wake, while depositing basalts etc. upon the uplifted and upper areas.

What we are going to see is that these observations get even more interesting with magnetic and geo-topical overlays!

Figure 9 - Gravity BA overlay with topological; is it not clear that the bifurcation is happening not only at a different vector, but also east of the BRMC, and inside the Mesozoic, not the Piedmont⁵? It is happening at the junction of the Mesozoic and “Blue Ridge” zone, but the mountain chain is clearly ended. Let us directly compare this result with the magnetic overlay on topological:

⁵ Economically important rocks and minerals found in the Piedmont include soapstone, kyanite, slate, vermiculite, and feldspar. Various igneous and metamorphic rocks are used for aggregate (crushed stone) and dimension stone. Gold, pyrite, and other metallic minerals are also present.” <https://varockshop.com/archive/the-geology-of-virginia>

Figure 10 - Aeromagnetic Overlay; the author cannot seriously be the only person that sees the dyadic bifurcation in the BRMC, especially at the Shenandoah National Park... nor the obvious query: why is there more magnetic concentration in the Piedmont east of the Blue Ridge, than in all but the concentrated “volcanic” minerals at the peaks? Nor can the author be the only one seeing the magnetic anomaly to the west, or how the magnetic turbulence is bisecting the gravity concentrations in Figure 9. Finally, the author cannot be the only one to notice the magnetic escarpment coming from the southwest, which inexplicably (via standard geomorphology) cuts into the BRMC. Note the area near to Waynesboro, called Avon, which has the bow shock-like arc in the topology, and shows an unusual magnetic escarpment with easterly concentrations in lowlands! Credit: author et al.

Finally we make the total overlay:

Figure 11 - Complete Overlay, with mineral map contrast turned high to bring out boundaries; it is clear to see that the mineral overlay is not perfect; but even then we can see that the magnetics and gravitics both display antithetical behaviors to the accumulations at the mountain chains. More mass, more minerals should mean more gravity and magnetism, in theory. But what we see here is quite the opposite. We see that in the places of volcanic type rocks, indeed magnetic concentrations, but otherwise, most accumulations are in the Mesozoic and Piedmont, or strangely cutting into the coastal plains. Meanwhile the BRM chain is often bisected by different magnetic and gravity behaviors from the west side to the east. Credit: Author et al.

Figure 12 - We can definitely see that the magnetic concentration is occurring **east** of the Blue Ridge Mountain chain. And after all, the concentration is strongest in various parts of the BRM chain, and then the upper Piedmont. Meanwhile, the magnetic escarpment cuts right through the BRM chain, and this confirms Figure 11.

Conclusion

The author wants to emphasize that these studies are not exactly conclusive. However they do sever the mainstream from the front edge of the study, and puts electrogeology at the forefront. That's exactly fine with the author and community of EPEMC (including the "Electric Universe.") But the author cautions the community from deciding the issue is settled. It isn't settled. It is, however, firmly in our court. These studies and cross-comparisons make the following very clear:

- Anomalies can cut right through layers, and ignore the limits imposed by mineral changes,
- Concentration levels do not match deposition volumes.
- Escarpments are often on different vectors than formations.
- Bifurcation of the fields from east to west bisects the mountain chain, and this is not explainable with volcanism or stratigraphy.
- Magnetic concentrations at the Shenandoah portion are uncoincidentally correlative to the high energy flux *felt* at the location, caused by the "volcanic" morphology⁶... though that appears to be the result of electric transmutation, not of true volcanism. Even the mainstream doesn't maintain they are a chain of volcanoes, only uplifted charnockites⁷.
- The main bulk of magnetism is east of the granite, located in the Piedmont and Mesozoic, which itself is bifurcated by the gravity anomaly. The "Y" shape of that anomaly *is* related to the Mesozoic layer, but the magnetic concentration running through this "Y" indicates an electro-gravitic signature, and not a matter of the **mass** of mountains. Contrary to expectations of mainstream physics.

⁶ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Blue_Ridge_Mountains

⁷ <https://blueridgediscoverycenter.org/blueridgediscoverycenterblog/1/26/2019geologyexpedition>

Figure 13 - Detailed Mineralogic and Magnetic Overlay; credit: Esri/USGS/author

Figure 14 - Transition of overlay (gif); click image to enlarge to video; credit: author/makeagif⁸

⁸ <https://youtu.be/HwvH6zd64Zw>

References

1. "Geology and Mineral Resources," Virginia. Department of Energy, 2021, <https://www.energy.virginia.gov/geology/geologymineralresources.shtml>
2. "MESS 0025 - MIMS 2.10.1-.5 - Sir Arthur Doyle's Gift: Investigation, the MIMS of empirical observation," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/89349129/MESS_0025_MIMS_2_10_1_5_Sir_Arthur_Doyle_s_Gift_Investigation_the_MIMS_of_empirical_observation
3. "Blue Ridge Mountains," Wikipedia, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Blue_Ridge_Mountains
4. The Blue Ridge: A Geological Autobiography, Blue Ridge Discovery Center, 2019, <https://blueridgediscoverycenter.org/blueridgediscoverycenterblog/1/26/2019geologyexpedition>
5. "MESS0029 GEO 2 25 Blue Ridge Magnetic Anomaly Hyperfocus," Youtube, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HwvH6zd64Zw>
6. "MESS0018: GEO 2.2 -Electrogeology evidence in macrolytic magnetic and gravitic field anomalies in VA, NC, and KY.," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/88366256/MESS0018_GEO_2_2_Electrogeology_evidence_in_macrolytic_magnetic_and_gravitic_field_anomalies_in_VA_NC_and_KY